

Dark Web

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The dark web, accessed through special software such as Tor, is a part of the Internet that is invisible to search engines and standard browsing methods. It offers encrypted and anonymous data exchange, often associated with illegal activities such as drug trafficking and information theft. But it also serves a vital function for journalists and activists in repressive regimes, providing a means to evade censorship and surveillance. Conceptually, the dark web is a subset of the deep web, which includes all unindexed content, as opposed to the easily accessible surface web. Researchers exploring the dark web face unique challenges due to the volatile nature of its content and the ethical implications of studying potentially illegal activity. Despite its notoriety, the dark web remains a relatively understudied area within political communication research, suggesting a gap in comprehensive understanding of its impact and infrastructure.

Dark Web; Tor Network; Anonymity; Encryption; Internet Censorship; Cybersecurity

The dark web is an anonymous and encrypted network and special software, such as Tor, is required to access its content. Often, the dark web is associated with illegal activities, but journalists and activists also use the anonymity of the network to circumvent state censorship or surveillance. In addition to the dark web, the terms "dark net", "hidden web" or "hidden services" are also commonly used. The entry provides a brief, non-technical overview of the characteristics of the dark web, ways to access it, potential obstacles, and insights from current research.

Conceptual remarks

To better understand the access and distribution of content and information on the internet, the metaphor of an iceberg is often used. This illustrates that only a small part of the content is visible, similar to the tip of an iceberg above the water. The larger and more important part remains hidden beneath the surface. The visible information - i.e. the tip of the iceberg - forms what is known as the "surface web" (or "clear web"). Internet pages, such as news sites, or shopping platforms, can be visited via conventional browsers. These pages are public and indexed by search engines. However, much more content exists below the surface in what is known as the "deep web". This refers to content that is characterized by access barriers and not being publicly visible. This, e.g., includes the intranet of companies or public authorities, cloud storage or content behind paywalls. The dark web is defined as a small and specific part of the deep web (Soldner, 2023; Soldner et al., 2022). Notably, the metaphor has also led to the scope of the dark web being massively overestimated.

The following conceptual characteristics define a network as a dark web: 1) The pages of the network cannot be found via standard search engines, such as Google or Bing, i.e., websites are not indexed, 2) access happens via a specific browser, such as Tor, and 3) data exchange is anonymous and encrypted. Clearnet websites are also sometimes classified as part of the dark web, especially when they are trading platforms for illegal goods or forums. However, the key distinction between the dark web and the clear web lies in the unique routing systems that are set up to ensure anonymity for both the users visiting the websites and the individuals hosting these sites (Gehl, 2018, p. 8).

The public often associates the dark web with illicit trade, acting as a bustling marketplace for drugs, stolen goods, pornography, cryptocurrencies, or hacking services. However, the benefits of an anonymous and encrypted network extend beyond illegal endeavors and trade. The dark web has also been used (and studied) as a tool for overcoming state censorship and for secure communication, for example, for whistleblowers.

The Tor network

There are various networks for accessing content that falls under the term dark web, including I2P ("Invisible Internet Project") and "Freenet". The best known, however, is the Tor network. There are similarities between the technologies, such as decentralization, but also differences in the network architecture (Graham & Pitman, 2020). The acronym Tor stands for "The Onion Router".¹ This is an allusion to the network architecture, which resembles an onion as it has different nodes or "layers", allowing users to anonymously access content on both the dark and clear web.

Tor was developed by David Goldschlag, Mike Reed, and Paul Syverson, starting in 1995 at the U.S. Naval Research Laboratory - a research division of the U.S. Department of Defense. In 2003, the source code was released under an open-source license. In 2006, The Tor Project Inc. was founded as a non-profit organization based in Boston and has been responsible for Tor ever since.² Funding for Tor is based on support from government agencies, organizations, NGOs and individual donations. According to the 2021-2022 financial report, the budget amounts to around 6.9 million dollars, which is many times higher than that of I2P or Freenet. In the financial year in question, around 53.5% of revenue came from support from the US government.³ Its origin and the substantial financing by the US authorities characterize one of the many contradictions of the dark web and the Tor network in particular: While Tor was initiated and funded by the government, it is used to evade government control. At the same time, it secures communication across the world (Davis & Arrigo, 2021; Ngo et al., 2023). The interests in an anonymous and encrypted network are therefore manifold.

The following is a brief and non-technical introduction to the principle of Tor: Tor follows the structure of the Internet, which is based on communication via IP addresses. These addresses allow both users and websites to be identified and browser histories to be tracked. Tor adds an additional layer of protection to this structure with its onion encryption technology. With this technique, a data packet, such as a request to a website, is not exchanged directly between IP addresses, but is, instead, redirected through a series of nodes. Each of these nodes is only known to the immediately preceding node from which it receives the packet and the subsequent node to which it forwards the packet. Although this does not make it (technically) impossible to identify the information, it does make it significantly more difficult, thus in most cases

¹ Despite the acronym, Tor is not spelled "TOR".

² See <https://www.torproject.org/about/history/>.

³ See <https://blog.torproject.org/transparency-openness-and-our-2021-and-2022-financials/>.

communication is nearly anonymous. Tor can be used both as an anonymous browser and as a server to host websites with the *.onion extension (Moore & Rid, 2016).

While websites on the clear web usually have a meaningful second-level domain (e.g. the BBC) with a corresponding top-level domain (".com") such as "bbc.com", websites on the Tor network have a cryptic sequence of characters. In 2021, the V2 Onion service with 16 characters was discontinued and replaced by the further development V3 (with 56 characters). These domains can only be accessed via the Tor network, such as the BBC's Tor mirror.⁴ It is in the nature of the Tor network that only a few metrics about usage are collected, but interesting and machine-readable metadata can be obtained for research via <https://metrics.torproject.org/>. This includes usage statistics from different countries, performance information, and network traffic. The latter reveals that the use of "hidden services" accounts for only a very small part of the Tor network. Instead, Tor is mostly used for anonymous access to the clear web (Hoeller et al., 2021; Moore & Rid, 2016).

Research on the Dark Web

Researchers interested in the dark web are likely to be disappointed when using Tor for the first time, due to the lack of indexing and the specific nature of the *.onion domain. An overview of popular dark web pages is promised by so-called hidden wikis with documentation of dark web domains. However, these hidden wikis should be viewed with caution for various reasons: Although the wikis offer a quick overview and, thus, access to dark web sites, the focus here is often specifically on illegal content, such as drug dealing or credit card fraud. Generally, the hidden wikis confirm prejudices about the predominantly illegal content of the dark web. However, it is completely unclear what criteria are used to select the link lists and who is behind them. It can, hence, be assumed that some of the links may be redirected to fake stores. Another disappointment when using Tor for the first time is the inaccessibility of many websites. There are various possible reasons for this: For example, sites on the Tor network are often the target of DDoS attacks, which results in high failure rates or long loading times.⁵ In principle, many sites only have a short half-life, which leads to their disappearance (and, thus, to the loss of the complete communication history). This is also because the pages are hosted and administered by individuals or groups of volunteers, so that even a simple lack of continued interest can lead

⁴ The mirror can be accessed via the following domain using the Tor browser:
<https://www.bbcnewsd73hkzno2ini43t4gblxvycyac5aw4gnv7t2rccijh7745uqd.onion/>.

⁵ DDoS is short for Distributed Denial of Service, a method where an attacker overwhelms a target service with excessive traffic, making it inaccessible to genuine users.

to a page being shut down. Finally, dark web sites are regularly taken over by security authorities if illegal activities or trafficking are taking place there.

Various disciplines from cryptography to criminology, have been dealing with the phenomenon of the dark web. The main research on the dark web and Tor carried out in computer science, while criminology or security research examine, for example, interaction on dark markets, deviant behavior, such as drug use and fraud, cryptocurrencies, or terrorism. In terms of political communication research, researchers can address various analytical levels. For example, the question arises as to how state censorship and surveillance affect internet use and what role anonymous networks, such as Tor, play in this (Jardine, 2018). The reception and spread of conspiracy theories or political attitudes in general can also be a topic of study in the context of the dark web to better understand social phenomena including extremism, the spread of disinformation, or political movements. For example, there is evidence that right-wing extremist or misogynist groups use infrastructure on the dark web due to deplatforming on the clear web (Hoffman et al., 2020).

Collecting Dark Web data

Both quantitative and qualitative research designs have been employed in empirical studies of the dark web and its use, while dedicated methodological research is still quite sparse in this area (Ngo et al., 2023). In relation to digital ethnography, Barratt and Maddox (2016) offer a workflow for conducting research in environments with sensitive or illegal activities and discuss the ethical and legal challenges for researchers.

The quantitative collection of data is not a trivial task, and the naive use of a web crawler is not recommended. Compared to political communication research on traditional social media, data collection on the dark web has several prerequisites and is subject to specific hurdles and restrictions: To begin with, forums or chats that may be of interest for a research question are not indexed via search engines and cannot be found easily. Also, the half-life of forums or chat rooms is crucial, so that previously larger forums may become inaccessible without further notice. Relevant research units could be identified via link collections, some of which can also be found on the clear web, or - with caution - via hidden wikis. It should also be mentioned here that all too obvious references to illegal content in a forum (e.g., for hacking) only serve to buy paid access - these are simply attempts at fraud or phishing. The latter are a major problem on the dark web (Steinebach et al., 2021). Nevertheless, paying for hacking services or buying drugs is possible and has been tested by researchers (Hyslip & Holt, 2019; Jurásek et al., 2021; Maimon et al., 2020). Not all marketplaces are fraudulent, but researchers should always be

skeptical about the sites they visit. Prior research on the clear web (e.g. via Reddit) is probably necessary and appropriate time should be planned in the study design to identify forums or pages, e.g., using the snowball sampling method. Although the onion-sites are not indexed, there are often links and references to other pages. This allows researchers to gradually identify relevant pages.

As mentioned, automated data collection on the dark web is not a trivial task and is associated with various risks. In addition to anti-crawling mechanisms, the onion-websites can also contain malicious code and, thus, infect researchers' computers with malware. A minimum requirement for automated data collection is the use of secure systems that do not provide access to local networks. Alternatively, cloud services can also be used for collection, although some providers prohibit this use to protect the systems from risks. Furthermore, filters or other mechanisms must be used to prevent the automated storage of content relevant to criminal or copyright law (Benjamin et al., 2019). Taking these risks into account, it is advisable for researchers interested in the dark web to consider and make use of existing data repositories. One interesting data source is the "Darknet Market Archives".⁶ This archive contains data from known dark markets between 2013 – 2015 (Branwen et al., 2015). However, openly accessible data is often outdated, requiring new data to be collected.

Conclusion and future research

The entry offered a brief overview of the conceptual characteristics of the dark web and discussed access, particularly through the Tor network. As stated before, the public perception of the dark web is characterized by illegal content or trade, which has sometimes contributed to mystification and urban legends. Although dark markets cannot be dismissed out of hand, for researchers with an interest in them, they initially lead to a lot of "noise" that must be filtered out to be able to investigate structures and actors on the dark web. A relevant part of the research time, hence, likely must be spent on reducing such "noise". Despite its reputation as a haven for illegal transactions, the importance of the dark web is complex and offers a unique mix of anonymity and freedom in the digital age. Although there is a broad research landscape, until now, the dark web only represents a niche topic within the social sciences. Methodological issues related to ethics or data quality may be addressed in future research. Additionally, studies could examine specific conspiracy narratives or political extremism in forums and chat rooms, along with the connections between the dark web and the clear web.

⁶ See <https://gwers.net/dnm-archive>.

References

- Barratt, M. J., & Maddox, A. (2016). Active engagement with stigmatised communities through digital ethnography. *Qualitative Research, 16*(6), 701–719.
- Benjamin, V., Valacich, J. S., & Chen, H. (2019). DICE-E: A Framework for Conducting Darknet Identification, Collection, Evaluation with Ethics. *MIS Quarterly, 43*(1), 1–22.
- Branwen, G., Christin, N., Décary-Hétu, D., Andersen, R. M., StExo, Presidente, E., Anonymous, Lau, D., Sohhlz, D. K., Cakic, V., Buskirk, V., Whom, McKenna, M., & Goode, S. (2015). *Dark Net Market archives, 2011-2015* [dataset].
<https://gwern.net/dnm-archive>
- Davis, S., & Arrigo, B. (2021). The Dark Web and anonymizing technologies: Legal pitfalls, ethical prospects, and policy directions from radical criminology. *Crime, Law and Social Change, 76*(4), 367–386.
- Gehl, R. (2018). *Weaving the dark web: Legitimacy on Freenet, Tor, and I2P*. The MIT Press.
- Graham, R., & Pitman, B. (2020). Freedom in the wilderness: A study of a Darknet space. *Convergence, 26*(3), 593–619.
- Hoeller, T., Roland, M., & Mayrhofer, R. (2021). On the state of V3 onion services. *Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2021 Workshop on Free and Open Communications on the Internet, 50–56*.
- Hoffman, B., Ware, J., & Shapiro, E. (2020). Assessing the Threat of Incel Violence. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism, 43*(7), 565–587.
- Hyslip, T. S., & Holt, T. J. (2019). Assessing the Capacity of DRDoS-For-Hire Services in Cybercrime Markets. *Deviant Behavior, 40*(12), 1609–1625.
- Jardine, E. (2018). Tor, what is it good for? Political repression and the use of online anonymity-granting technologies. *New Media & Society, 20*(2), 435–452.
- Jurásek, B., Čmelo, I., Svoboda, J., Čejka, J., Svozil, D., & Kuchař, M. (2021). New psychoactive substances on dark web markets: From deal solicitation to forensic analysis of purchased substances. *Drug Testing and Analysis, 13*(1), 156–168.
- Maimon, D., Wu, Y., Stubler, N., & Singirikonda, P. (2020). *Extended Validation in the Dark Web: Evidence from Investigation of the Certification Services and Products Sold on Darknet Markets* (2; EBCS Reports). https://scholarworks.gsu.edu/ebsc_reports/2
- Moore, D., & Rid, T. (2016). Cryptopolitik and the Darknet. *Survival, 58*(1), 7–38.

- Ngo, F. T., Marcum, C., & Belshaw, S. (2023). The Dark Web: What Is It, How to Access It, and Why We Need to Study It. *Journal of Contemporary Criminal Justice*, 39(2), 160–166.
- Soldner, F. (2023). The Dark Web. A Brief Introduction. *Easy Social Sciences*, 69, 1827.
- Soldner, F., Kleinberg, B., & Johnson, S. (2022). Trends in online consumer fraud: A data science perspective. In Y. Hanoch & S. Wood, *A Fresh Look at Fraud* (1st ed., pp. 167–191). Routledge.
- Steinebach, M., Zenglein, S., & Brandl, K. (2021). Phishing detection on tor hidden services. *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, 36, 301117.